

Photo-reactions of 11*H*-Dibenzo[*c, f*][1,2]diazepines

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IN view of the large number of compounds that could be formed by hydrogen abstraction and oxygen insertion reactions of the photoexcited nitro groups in 2,2'-dinitrodiphenyl methanes¹⁻³ and their subsequent photoreactions, it seemed of

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interest to examine the photoreactions of 11*H*-dibenzo[*c, f*][1,2]diazepines. Previous investigation⁴ on the parent compound (1a) of this series in acidified ethanol resulted in the isolation of dibenzo[*c, f*][1,2]diazepin-11-one (2a), 2,2'-diaminobenzophenone (3a) and 2,2'-diaminodiphenylmethane (4a) as products. Our investigation on the photochemical behaviour of 3,8-dichloro/dibromo 11*H*-dibenzo[*c, f*][1,2]diazepines (1b, c) in the same solvent system led to the isolation of their 11-ethoxy derivatives (1e, g) as a new type of product.

When a 0.02*M* solution of 1b in acidified ethanol was irradiated for 48 h, about 60% conversion of the starting material was observed. Chromatographic separation of the constituents of the resulting mixture afforded 3,8-dichloro-11*H*-11-ethoxydibenzo[*c, f*][1,2]diazepine (1e), the unchanged starting material, 3,8-dichlorodibenzo[*c, f*][1,2]diazepin-11-one (2b), 2,2'-diamino-4,4'-dichlorobenzophenone (3b) and 2,2'-diamino-4,4'-dichlorodiphenylmethane (4b) (Scheme 1). The irradiation of 1c in acidified ethanol for 42 h followed by work-up yielded the corresponding photoproducts 1g, 2c, 3c and 4c.

- a ; X = H, R = H
- b ; X = Cl, R = H
- c ; X = Br, R = H
- d ; X = Cl, R = OH
- e ; X = Cl, R = OC₂H₅
- f ; X = Br, R = OH
- g ; X = Br, R = OC₂H₅

Scheme 1

The occurrence of no photochemical reaction in neutral solvents indicates that the conjugate acid of 11*H*-dibenzo[*c, f*][1,2]diazepine is the species which undergoes photochemical change. The diazepines are known to be sufficiently basic to be protonated in weakly acidic solutions and it is indicated by their ultraviolet-visible absorption data⁵. From the nature of the products isolated in the photoreactions of 1b, c it is evident that a disproportionation reaction has occurred. The occurrence of no reaction on treatment of 1b, c with acidic ethanol in the dark for several days indicates that the disproportionation reaction is a photoinduced one. This appears to be parallel to the photoreactions observed for azo compounds in acidic solutions⁶⁻⁸. The plausible mechanistic path involving photoinduced intermolecular hydride transfer³ has been delineated in Scheme 2. It may be mentioned here that 5,6-dihydro-11*H*-dibenzo[*c, f*][1,2]diazepines (7) are known¹⁰ to undergo disproportionation in acidic medium giving 2,2'-diaminodiphenylmethane (4).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in an oil immersion bath. The starting materials (1b, c) were obtained by LiAlH₄ reduction of related 4,4'-dihalo-2,2'-dinitrodiphenylmethanes¹¹.

Irradiation of 3,8-dichloro-11*H*-dibenzo[*c, f*][1,2]-diazepine (1b): A solution of 1b (1 g) in acidified ethanol (2 ml concentrated H₂SO₄ and 160 ml ethanol) was irradiated for 48 h using a HPK 125W high pressure mercury lamp. The photolysate was then neutralised with sodium bicarbonate and filtered to remove Na₂SO₄. The filtrate after partial evaporation was diluted with water and then extracted with benzene. The combined benzene extracts was evaporated and the residue chromatographed on a column of neutral alumina. Elution with light petrol afforded 1e (145 mg), crystallising from light petrol as orange yellow needles, m.p. 129° (Found: C, 59.0; H, 3.8; N, 9.2. C₁₅H₁₃Cl₂N₂O requires: C, 58.8; H, 3.9; N, 9.1%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 250, 309 and 425 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 050w, 2 900s, 2 850w, 1 580w, 1 560m, 1 380m, 1 460m, 1 380m, 1 330m, 1 200w, 1 160m, 1 130m and 1 090s cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.2 (3H, t, J 6 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 3.44 (2H, q, J 6 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 4.7 (1H, H-11), 7.32 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, H-1 and H-10), 7.52 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, H-2 and H-9) and 7.76 (2H, s, H-4 and H-7); m/z 306 (M⁺, 59%), 279(11), 277(15), 271(12), 261(13), 262(29), 263(13), 264(20), 251(24), 249(3), 243(18), 233(34), 235(25), 217(13), 215(43), 201(33), 200(18), 198(100), 197(11), 188(24) and 163(44). Continued elution with light petrol gave the unchanged starting material (400 mg), m.p. 205°. Further elution of the column with light petrol-benzene (2 : 1, v/v) afforded 2b (500 mg), m.p. and m.m.p. 234° and 3b (51 mg) m.p. and m.m.p. 131°. Final elution of the column with benzene gave 4b (80 mg), m.p. and m.m.p. 120°.

Irradiation of 1c: A solution of 1c (1 g) in acidified ethanol was irradiated for 42 h and worked

up as above. Chromatography on neutral alumina afforded 1g (150 mg), m.p. 132° (Found : C, 45.5 ; H, 2.9 ; N, 7.7. $C_{15}H_{18}N_2Br_2O$ requires : C, 45.5 ; H, 3.0 ; N, 7.77%) ; λ_{max} (EtOH) 250, 306 and 427 nm ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 050w, 2 950m, 2 900m, 1 560m, 1 480m, 1 460m, 1 380s, 1 330m, 1 200m, 1 160s, 1 120m, 1 110m and 1 080s cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.2 (3H, t, J 6 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 3.4 (2H, q, J 6 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 4.0 (1H, s, H-11), 7.34 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, H-1 and H-10), 7.54 (2H, d J 6 Hz, H-2 and H-9) and 7.96 (2H, s, H-4 and H-7) ; m/z (M^+ 36%), 394(68), 392(35), 369(18), 367(30), 365(15), 353(22), 351(43), 349(21), 325(21), 324(6), 323(45), 322(7), 321(22), 245(44), 244(100), 243(89), 242(8), 241(60) and 164(30). The other components were the unchanged starting material 1c (250 mg), 2c (62 mg), 3c (63 mg), m.p. and m.m.p.¹² 141° and 4c (85 mg) m.p. and m.m.p.¹² 136°.

The authentic samples of 2b and 2c were prepared by the reported procedure¹. 3b, c and 4b, c were prepared by reducing 4,4'-dichloro/4,4'-dibromo-2,2'-dinitrobenzophenone and 2,2'-dinitrodiphenylmethane using Sn/HCl.

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